

Evolution of Religious Tourism: Concept, Segmentation and Development of New Identities

Mariana BĂLAN¹

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ABSTRACT

During the last decades of the 21st century, world tourism has diversified its forms of manifestation internationally, trying to capitalize on the most valuable cultural and religious objectives in the religious cultural heritage of a country. Between tourism and culture, respectively between tourism and religion there are countless interactions and combinations based on the relationship between the cultural objective / sacred place and the motivation of the tourist according to which several aspects can be analyzed. Tourism, in general, be it religious or cultural, is the way in which a country becomes known to the world, and through which other people can see the natural resources, the tourist potential and the riches of that country. Romania has a cultural-historical and ethnofolkloric heritage of great value as well as tourist attractiveness and it is blessed with thousands of holy places and religious monuments, some dating back to the early Christian centuries. This paper presents a brief analysis of the evolution of religious tourism and the way existing concepts, paradigms and practices related to this type of tourism have evolved and changed over time. The performed analyzes show that the concept of religious tourism is gradually transformed and modernized over the years, going through phases of segmentation, creation of new market niches and development of new identities. The regions with cultural-religious tourist potential in Romania are also presented, as well as the activities that can grow and help the development of this type of tourism in our country.

1. Introduction

In 1998, Cuvelier stated that “tourism is a set of practices associated with the temporary abandonment of residence, with the aim of recreating, restoring, the basic human need for diversity, discovering new knowledge, experiences and encounters.”

Hunziker defined tourism as “the set of relationships and phenomena resulting from the movement and stay of persons outside their place of residence, as long as the movement and stay are not motivated by a permanent establishment or a lucrative activity” (Postelnicu, 1997: 12).

Religious tourism is one of the most important forms of tourism, its main objective being the participation in religious events that influence the diversity of religious tourism offers. The main purpose of religious tourism is to develop human spirituality, culture, the way a person receives the experience of cooperation or

¹ Professor; Researcher I, Institute for Economic Forecasting, “Costin C. Kirițescu” National Institute for Economic Research, Romanian Academy, Bucharest, Romania; dr.mariana.balan@gmail.com

involvement with the place of living, people, culture and religion. This form of tourism can play a significant role in the overall goals of society and in establishing trusting relationships between people of all cultures and religions.

“Most of the world’s great religious centers, past and present, have been destinations for pilgrimages - think of the Vatican, Mecca, Jerusalem, Bodh Gaya (where Buddha was enlightened), or Cahokia (the enormous Native American complex near St. Louis). They are monuments for spiritual travelers, who often came great distances, to gawk at and be stirred by [such sites]... What it suggests... is that the human sense of the sacred - and the human love of a good show - may have given rise to civilization itself” Mann (2011) showed in *The Birth of Religion*, and thus highlighted the complex relationship between the origins of civilization and religion.

Former Secretary-General of the World Tourism Organization Taleb Rifai said that “religious tourism can be one of the most effective tools for promoting inclusive and sustainable development”. Within this context, three main benefits of religious tourism can be identified: (1) raising awareness of the common heritage of humanity and providing resources for conservation; (2) contribution to local development; (3) building and strengthening cultural agreements.

It can be said that tourism and its associated practices interact with religious life and religious institutions in almost every corner of the world. Thus, from the mysterious ruins of Machu Picchu in the Peruvian Andes to the monumental pyramids of Giza in Egypt, from the Amish communities in rural Pennsylvania to the snow-capped peaks of Mount Fuji in Japan, from Chartres in France to the Western Wall in Jerusalem, millions of tourists look for places full of religion every year. The relationship between religion and tourism, however, is much more complex than simple visits to religious sites by tourists. To understand this relationship, there are at least three approaches: spatial, historical and cultural, each highlighting different implications for religious life (when tourists enter a sacred precinct, the spaces become sacred depending on the historical, social and cultural contexts of certain religious traditions).

Lately, more and more tourists are interested in religious tourism. There are sacred places in the world, where many believers gather every year and where the number of tourists sometimes exceeds the number of believers. These are special places because they have certain legends and superstitions that attract tourists, and not only. Therefore, religious tourism is much wider than any other form of tourism, addressing several categories of people: people interested in architecture, people attracted by the vibration of the place, the meaning of the name given to that monument, the location, the legend heard about the place, the traditions and customs that are organized on a certain date in the calendar, etc.

During recent years, religious travel and tourism have settled in a much larger and more segmented market. According to statistics from the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development and the World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), cultural and heritage travel in 2019 accounted for more than 45% of total

international tourism, up 12 percent from 1995. Also according to UNWTO statistics, more than 1/3 of international trips are related to cultural tourism in which religious and spiritual aspects play an important role. Religious travel can be the main reason for a trip, but it can be part of a trip and can provide destinations with additional attractions.

In many countries, religious tourism is one of the most important and growing industrial sectors, growing jobs and incomes and with influences in most economic sectors. Sacred places in some countries provide a specific opportunity for the tourism industry to develop in a healthy and sustainable way.

2. Literature Review

Pilgrimages to holy sites are considered to be the oldest form of tourism (Apollo et al., 2020; Chélini & Branthomme, 1982; Collins-Kreiner, 2010, 2016b; Timothy & Olsen, 2006). They have contributed to the development of the geographical, cultural and civilizational horizons of nations of all world religions (Eliade, 1969; Jackowski, 2003; Singh, 2004). Pilgrimages are complex and changing phenomena, composed of a set of mutual interactions of religious, secular and natural factors that take place in the geographical space of pilgrimages (Cohen, 1992; Coleman & Eade, 2004; Collins-Kreiner, 2010, 2007; Digance, 2003; Eade & Sallnow, 1991; Kaszowski, 1996).

Although religious tourism has aroused the interest of many researchers and practitioners (Drule et al., 2012), it is still one of the least studied areas in tourism research (Timothy & Olsen, 2006). Given that there are a number of articles published in journals and recently published books or chapters in books that deal with various aspects of the interdependence between religion and tourism, for example, Cohen (1999); Tweed (2000); Epstein and Kheimets (2001); Jacobs (2001); Joseph and Kavoori (2001); Mattila et al. (2001); Shackley (2001); Tilson (2001); Collins-Kreiner and Kliot (2000) Collins-Kreiner (2002), Koskansky (2002), Bar and Cohen-Hattab (2003), Digance (2003), McNeill (2003), the literature continues to be fragmented and lacks holistic synthesis and conceptualization.

In his work *Homo Viator: From Pilgrimage to Religious Tourism Via the Journey*, Tomasi (2002) pointed out that in the 21st century, the distinction between faith-driven pilgrimage and tourism for cultural and recreational purposes is no longer valid because contemporary pilgrimages involve such a large number of people that they can only be organized in the same way as mass tourism.

Rinschede (1992), in his work *Forms of religious tourism* showed that religious tourism refers to visitors who are partially or exclusively motivated by religious reasons, an idea also supported by Smith (1992).

Țircă and Stănciulescu (2011) in their study showed that the reasons to travel to religious settlements are either for religious nature (to pray for different needs; to find God; for peace and quiet; to thank for goodness; for repentance; for guidance, and to strengthen their faith in God) or other than religious (curiosity, relaxation, and cultural motivation). In this context, Chand (2010) in his work also made a

comparison of the religious motivations of local visitors and other non-resident Indians visiting sacred sites in India.

Research by Hyde and Harman (2011) identified the reasons of Australian and New Zealand travelers for a secular pilgrimage to the Gallipoli battlefields in Turkey: spiritual, nationalist, family pilgrimage, friendship and travel. Collins-Kreiner and Kliot (2000), Triantafillidou et al., (2010) analyzed the reasons for visiting the Holy Land (faith, strong religious motives, prayer, reasons for recovery, health related to their baptism, etc.).

Vidić (2007) found in his study that the reasons for visiting Fruska Gora monasteries were, among other things, in order of importance: religion and spiritual reasons, healing, cultural reasons, and religious events and manifestations. Analyzing the non-religious motivations of 1600 Romanian Orthodox who visited a monastery, Drule et al., (2012) found that visitors are motivated mainly by a need for self-actualization, i.e. their desire to become better people.

Through research by Sharpley and Sundaram (2005), Egresi et al. (2012) found that religious sites were visited for their historical and cultural value, rather than for their sacred and spiritual value.

According to World Tourism Organization statistics, approximately 350 million people go on religious or cognitive/religious trips each year and visit major pilgrimage centers around the world (Griffin & Raj, 2017; Scaffidi Abbate & Di Nuovo, 2013). The promotion of shrines, the search for meeting places with oneself and with God, the renewal of tours along pilgrimage routes, the emergence of new pilgrimage routes, the development of the car industry and the expansion of tourist infrastructure in pilgrimage centers are the factors influencing the development of pilgrimages and religious tourism (Roszak, 2017; Mróz, 2019).

In recent years, researchers, governments and travel agencies have taken into account the growing number of religiously motivated travelers (or at least the increase in visits to sacred places), along with the general increase in cultural and heritage tourism. Places of worship are now seen as marketable tourist resources for travelers interested in cultural and historical sites. Mosques, churches, cathedrals, pilgrimage routes, sacred architecture are used prominently in tourism promotion literature, as evidenced by recent marketing efforts around 2000 and its millennial religious connotations (Olsen & Timothy, 1999). Therefore, modern travel patterns and activities can only be fully understood if religion is taken into account (Mattila et al., 2001).

3. Methodology

The analysis of the evolution of religious tourism and its new dimensions in the 21st century required a systematic revision of the specialized literature. The keywords “religious tourism”, “tourist motivation”, “pilgrimage”, “tourist behavior”, were the main criteria in the search and selection of scientific articles related to religious tourism.

The studied works aimed both to identify / explain the historical interdependence between tourism and religion, and to identify new trends in religious tourism, its segmentation and the transformation of this form of tourism in the current socio-economic context.

Also, based on specialized studies realized by Romanian researchers, statistics and studies of the Romanian Orthodox Church, a brief analysis of religious tourism in Romania was made.

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Historical relations between religion and tourism

The beginnings of the tourism activity date back to ancient times, when the trip was aimed at trade, religion, the Olympic Games, health, etc.

Religiously motivated tourism is a world phenomenon as old as religion itself and characteristic of all religious denominations (Lanczkowski, 1982). Menhirs, burial mounds, and kromlecks (Stonehenge) had the same purpose as today's cathedrals, being religious centers that attracted believers from far and near (Roussel, 1972).

Most often manifested in the form of pilgrimage, religious tourism involves a certain level of education and culture on the part of tourists in order to appreciate the objectives in terms of architecture, value and spiritual significance.

An important period for the development of the pilgrimage was ancient times. Traces of ancient pilgrimage routes have been preserved to this day, including pilgrimages to Egypt, Mesopotamia, Palestine, Arabia, Persia, India, China, Maya, Greece, and Rome. Archaeological studies also confirm the existence of places of worship that led to pilgrimages among the peoples of northern pre-Christian Europe, including the Celts, Germans and Slavs (Jackowski, 2003).

In ancient Egypt (3000 BC) there were pilgrimages to places of worship, pyramids, temples and the graves of close relatives or gods. Pilgrimages to the temples of Delphi and Corinth were of great importance and it can be said that the most popular forms of worship to the gods of ancient Greece were also sporting and cultural events. In order to host the pilgrimages, a network of facilities had to be developed: roads, accommodation, manufacturing special products especially for tourists, such as souvenirs, etc.

Typical religious journeys continued into the late Roman period, being associated primarily with pilgrimages to the Holy Land, and from the 3rd century AD, pilgrims also visited the Tombs of St. Peter and St. Paul in Rome, and later, pilgrimages to the Eternal City were an expression of fidelity to the Pope and took the form of a folding homage to him (Hamarneh, 1997; Mazur, 2010; Terzidou et al., 2008).

From the 10th century, the most important Christian pilgrimage route took from France to Santiago de Compostela in Spain, where the cult of St. James was worshiped (annually, over 500,000 pilgrims from all over Europe went there).

Pilgrimage to an ecclesiastical meeting became a spiritual asset during the Reformation of Martin Luther (when the role of relics in Christian spirituality began to be negotiated) (Hillerbrand, 2022).

The first travelers of the European Renaissance regularly visited churches, cathedrals, altars and other religious sites in order to study the art, architecture, culture and history of the nations they visited. Not infrequently, Renaissance travelers also condemned the practices of the religious people they met in such places. For example, the humanist Desiderius Erasmus (1466, 1467, or 1469–1536) pointed to the tension between the practices of early tourists and those of their fellow pilgrims in his colloquium, *A Pilgrimage for Religion's Sake*, published in 1526 (Tracy, 2022).

Since the middle of the 19th century, the sanctuary dedicated to the Virgin Mary of Lourdes has become a place of pilgrimage for both believers and the sick who seek relief / healing in the water source with healing properties near the cave. From the beginning of the 20th century, pilgrims went to Fatima (Portugal) and later, in the 1980s, to the shrine dedicated to the Virgin Mary of Medjugorje (Bosnia and Herzegovina).

Nowadays, among the places of pilgrimage frequented by Orthodox or Catholic believers, we can mention the city of Jerusalem (Church of the Holy Sepulcher), Mount Athos in Greece, the cities of Nazareth and Bethlehem, the Vatican, Mount Saint Michel, etc.

The pilgrimage is also specific to other beliefs and denominations. Thus, the Jews go on a pilgrimage to the Cave of the Patriarchs at Makpela near Hebron, where the tomb of Patriarch Abraham is located, as well as to Jerusalem. Every Muslim is obliged to go on pilgrimage to Mecca, the holy city where the Prophet Muhammad was born, at least once in his life. Other important places of pilgrimage for Muslims are the city of Medina, where the Prophet Muhammad lived, and the Al Aqsa Mosque in Jerusalem.

For Hindu believers, the great centers of pilgrimage are Haridwar (India) and especially the city of Benares, considered the center of the god Shiva, located on the banks of the river Ganges, where millions of pilgrims gather to purify themselves in sacred waters.

For Buddhists, the most important places of pilgrimage are the places where the Buddha lived and activated: Kapilavastru (the place where he was born), Bodgaya (the place where he received enlightenment), Benares (the place where he gave his first sermon) and Kasinara (where he died).

Therefore, it can be said that tourism has its roots in the religious pilgrimage. In fact, as well as categories of practice and experience, pilgrimage and tourism are easily confused.

In the contemporary context, pilgrims are often engaged in tourism activities: like tourists, they take pictures of the places they visit, buy souvenirs and gifts and benefit from the same transport and accommodation that tourists use. At the same time, tourists visiting religious sites, including pilgrimage destinations, sometimes

participate in religious practices. Studies in the field of religious tourism show that in modern societies, religious motivation seems to be less important than in ancient societies (Rinschede, 1992).

The analysis of the evolution of religious tourism highlights the fact that it is gradually transformed and modernized over the years, and goes through a phase of segmentation, creation of new market niches and development of new identities.

4.2. New trends in religious tourism

Nowadays, religious tourism has become a distinct segment of the world tourism market, gradually becoming a vast industry. If we quantify this industry in dollars, then the pilgrimage, religious excursions, meetings, conferences and religious camps will represent within this industry, distinct segments of billions of dollars. An impressive number of people (more than 8 million) have volunteered for projects to establish religious camps, including more than 120,000 churches. Also, many tour operators have started to develop religious circuits and there has been a significant increase in tourist programs and camps offered by churches and religious organizations, etc.

Since the 2000s, the definition of pilgrimage has been adapted to both traditional and modern secular religious journeys. A large number of tourists are looking for a variety of experiences, including enlightenment, knowledge, improved spiritual and physical well-being and challenge. The pilgrimage is currently in a rejuvenating stage and is therefore in the process of losing some of its religious attributes (which formed the initial basis of its identity as a distinct type of tourism) and is simultaneously developing new identities, such as secular pilgrimage, spiritual tourism, religious tourism, church tourism, dark tourism and transformational tourism (Collins-Kreiner, 2016a; Kiely, 2013).

Pilgrimage centers are modern means of promoting spirituality and culture in the local and international ecumenical context. Their role is to direct, coordinate and control the process of organizing pilgrimages. These centers offer a number of services such as: (1) trips for Christians from the country and abroad; (2) pilgrimages for pilgrims of other denominations; (3) city tours; (4) expeditions and study camps; (5) accommodation in guest houses and reception areas of churches; (6) advice on pilgrimages; (7) information services for religious tourism.

In the current literature, pilgrimage is considered a holistic phenomenon with religious and secular foundations (Collins-Kreiner, 2016a) which includes sites that can appear from both religious and secular contexts and new forms of pilgrimage are identified, such as:

- *New Age current/movement*: aims to create a “spirituality without boundaries or restrictive dogmas” (Drury, 2004), advocates a holistic vision, emphasizing that the mind, body and soul are interconnected, trying to create “a worldview that includes both science and spirituality” (Drury, 2004) by adopting both conventional science and other forms of frontier science;

- *modern secular pilgrimage*: an intermediate category between pilgrims belonging to a major world religion and pure tourism, is the modern concept of secular pilgrimage to places like the Himalayas, where the journey is neither purely pious nor pure for pleasure, but is in a to some extent a “compromise”;

- *dark tourism*: the curiosity of some people to get to know bad places, places where natural disasters have taken place (such as Chernobyl), famous crimes or genocides attract thousands of tourists every year, thus becoming a global phenomenon;

- *spiritual tourism*: characterized by presentations of historical spirituality of tourist objectives and spiritual activities, aims at presentations of sacred places, of events explained in the Divine Laws, helps people to deify, to understand, to communicate in the spirit of divine teachings;

- *heritage and pilgrimage tourism*: the fastest growing segment of the tourism industry, as there is a growing trend towards specialization among tourists, evident by the increasing volume of tourists seeking adventure, culture, history, archeology and interaction with local people. This form of tourism is important because it has a positive economic and social impact, establishes and strengthens the identity, helps to preserve the cultural heritage, along with, culture facilitates harmony and understanding between people, supports culture and helps to renew tourism;

- *cultural pilgrimage*: where destinations for such pilgrims include historical sites of national or cultural importance (an artist’s home, a place where an important event took place or an iconic destination).

The intensive growth of religious tourism on the global market, its complex structure, as well as its dynamic qualitative and quantitative changes have led to a market segmentation of this form of tourism. The segmentation of the tourist market offers conditions for the creation of competitive tourist products, based on the study of the demand of specific groups of consumers, thus putting into practice one of the most important principles of marketing - the principle of focusing on consumer needs.

Because there is no single method of segmentation in the literature, different authors have presented various criteria for segmentation of the tourism market in general, and that of religious tourism in particular. Thus, Boo and Jones (2009) considered the travel *motivation* of tourists as a criterion for segmenting the tourism market (however, the application of this criterion puts a limitation of research, because motivation does not take into account the attitude and understanding of tourists). Nam et al. (2011) consider that a combination of *motivations and lifestyles* of tourists would provide a better segmentation basis for the religious tourism market.

Cost-based segmentation has been used to group tourists based on their spending patterns (Legohérel & Wong, 2006; Legohérel, 1998). Studies to this end have shown that spending-based segmentation is irrelevant, as it has been observed that people seeking spirituality are less interested / price conscious (Yeh et al., 2009; Raj & Morpeth, 2007; Hill, 2002; Campo, 1998).

Also, much of the research in recent years on religious tourism has focused on practical *motivational* issues (Cohen, 2003; Collins-Kreiner, 2004; Nieminen, 2012); *satisfaction* (Canoves & Prat Forga, 2016; Krešić et al., 2012); *religious tourism experiences* (Bond et al., 2014; Hughes et al., 2013) and *decision-making patterns* in religious travel (Henderson, 2010; Kunst et al., 2009; Churches Conservation Trust & Churches Tourism Association, 2006), but also on the role of religious tourism as an agent of societal transformation (which can promote both personal and societal transformation, mainly by emphasizing spirituality or providing experiences that make tourists reflect on their life and worldviews).

Promoting religious tourism as critical system thinking leads to new approaches and practices of open, emancipatory and transformative systems (Boluk et al., 2019; Jackson, 2001, 2010; Roxas et al., 2020) and helps boost sustainable tourism. (if the future impact on visitors, industry, the environment and communities is taken into account). Sustainable religious tourism is based both on consolidating a relationship-oriented perspective (Beritelli & Laesser, 2011) and on building organizational intelligence as a sustainable framework for generating social and economic change (Brătianu et al., 2006).

The motivations for tourists to visit religious sites are based on the development of emotions and the experience of spiritual values as sources of understanding production of knowledge as a dynamic and transformation of knowledge. Religious tourism generates sustainable organizational models of hospitality that support community involvement and cultural managerial policies in line with travelers' expectations (Gazzola et al., 2018; Gazzola et al., 2019b; Grechiet et al., 2015). New technologies and social networking platforms (as pillars of the digital age of communication) allow, on the one hand, to improve the co-creation of the travel experience, and on the other hand, to rediscover a new perspective for addressing the sustainable development of religious tourism. Thus, IT&C helps reshaping the tourist experience (because they have a strong influence on the way religious sites, customs and traditions are perceived) while allowing travel agencies and organizations that manage religious sites to listen to the voices and opinions of tourists (De Ascaniis & Cantoni, 2016).

The COVID-19 pandemic has had a significant impact on the religious tourism market. Several major religious holidays have been affected by travel restrictions. Places of worship such as churches, mosques, temples and synagogues had to change worship rituals to reduce the spread of COVID-19. Altarpieces in the Middle East have been closed or restricted to visitors in an attempt to stop the spread of the virus. The impact of the health crisis is already visible in many countries, especially in those where religious tourism is a major source of income and job creation.

4.3. Brief analysis of religious tourism in Romania

Romania is a country with an exceptional tourist potential, and the cultural and religious tourist objectives are among the most valuable in the world, being visited especially by many European tourists, as well as Asians eager for culture.

However, in Romania, religion returned to the attention of researchers during the period 1990-2000. Trebici (1998) highlighted the role of religion as a determining factor for many social, economic, demographic processes, etc. "There is a direct link between the 'heritage' of each religious denomination, the family's value system and the motivation for pilgrimage, to the detriment of modern methods of promotion. These aspects are very important in rural areas, in regions such as Bucovina or Maramureș, where the traditions and inherited values have been better preserved. From a cultural point of view, these areas are special, especially because traditions and values cannot be separated from the religious element" (Trebici, 1998).

All regions in Romania have important pilgrimage centers, both religious and secular. The best known are in Bucovina (Voronet, Sucevița, Putna, Moldovița), Oltenia (Tismana, Polovragi, Cozia, Hurez, Dintr-un lemn, Frasinei), Dobrogea (Cocoș, Celic Dere, Saon, Dervent, Saint Andrew's cave), Transylvania (Râmet, Nicula), Bucharest (Cernica, Stavropoleos church, Darvari Hermitage, Patriarchate).

In Romania, there are approximately 18,300 churches and 637 monasteries, which represents a large number of well-preserved religious monuments, some of which have special historical and artistic values, with representative traditional architecture.

This religious heritage creates real opportunities for the development of religious tourism and pilgrimage in Romania.

There is also a well-known Romanian tradition of:

- pilgrimages to churches with holy relics (St. Paraskeva of the Balkans in Iași, St. Dimitrie the New from Basarabi in Bucharest, St. Gregory of Dekapolis at Bistrița Olteană Monastery, St. Martyr Filofteia at Curtea de Argeș, etc.), at churches with miraculous icons (Golia Monastery, Neamț Monastery, Bistrița Monastery, Durău Monastery, Agapia Monastery, etc.), or at the holy tombs (the bones of the first Christian martyr priests from the Cocoș Monastery in northern Dobrogea);
- visits to religious shrines (Dacian shrine at Sarmisegetuza Dacica in the Orăștie Mountains) and cultural-religious sites (monasteries in Moldova, Muntenia, Oltenia or Transylvania and Catholic cathedrals in Șumuleu, Brașov, Cluj-Napoca), or in areas where religious events take place (Christmas and New Year's Eve in the Maramureș area or in Bucovina);
- tours of important places of worship (circuit of monasteries in Bucovina, Moldova, Dobrogea).

An essential premise in the practice of religious tourism and pilgrimage is the need for knowledge and education, especially for young people, this being achieved either through youth religious camps (the Association of Christian-Orthodox Students in Romania organizes pilgrimages to monasteries throughout the country, groups of students from Bucharest and other university centers can participate in pilgrimages organized on Mount Athos), symposia on religious themes, cultural-Christian events, exhibitions of icons and worship objects or religious music concerts.

However, in Romania, the potential of religious tourism, based on the existence of many religious buildings, some of them promoted by both travel

agencies and the media, is not yet evaluated and used at its true value. Religious objectives are the main reason for some religious trips, but they can also be part of a complex tourist offer, which offers a religious destination as an additional attraction.

Many of the Romanian churches or monasteries are architectural and artistic monuments, considered (big) tourist attractions. Among the eight objectives in Romania inscribed in the UNESCO World Heritage (6 cultural and 2 natural), there are also the monasteries from Bucovina, the wooden churches from Maramureş, the Hurezi Monastery and the fortified churches from the Saxon villages from Transylvania.

In recent years, religious tourism in Romania has taken new forms of manifestation and is becoming a dynamic industry, which sells top tourist products, which is based on the quality of accommodation, food, leisure, transport and which addresses all categories of tourists (whether young or old). Romania is famous for its cultural-religious objectives and the highest density of places of worship, which can be important elements of the successful development of this form of tourism.

Religious tourism is constantly growing and demanded by all market segments, it is constantly growing and diversifying as a result of the combination with other forms of tourism.

5. Conclusion

Religion and tourism are inextricably linked. Religion is one of the most common motivations for travel, and religiously motivated travel, which remains one of the oldest and most basic forms of mobility in the world, is a major tourist phenomenon of the 21st century.

Most of the studies conducted to analyze the relationship between religion and tourism focus on either of them and pay little attention to the actual interaction between the two. This is surprising, as the development of tourism is difficult to understand without a thorough understanding of the pilgrimage of ancient times, with religious tourism and pilgrimage being important reasons for the global movement of people.

Religious tourism is that type of tourism that aims at visiting religious buildings with spiritual implications. From this point of view, it is not possible to make a clear distinction between those who visit these places for religious or for other reasons, as the impact that the visit has may or may not be religious.

The multitude of motivations for visiting sacred places actually corresponds to the complexity of modern man. In recent years, the pilgrim is looking for additional attractions, because visiting the holy places is not enough, it becomes a component of the journey. Therefore, it can be said that religious tourism is evolving, places of interest are undergoing transformations and there is a segmentation of the market of this form of tourism.

The activity of religious tourism in the context of world tourism is a part of the tourism industry in full development process, both as a phenomenon and as a consequence of the global economic health crises.

For many countries, religious tourism around its historical and religious heritage is a significant part of their total tourism market. Therefore, tourism is an economic branch that brings profit to many countries, and religious tourism brings income to places of worship and also leads to the development of localities that have such objectives.

Religious tourism in Romania is identified in various forms: visiting sacred monuments of worship, religious shrines, cultural and religious sites (monuments in Moldova, Oltenia, etc.), visiting religious destinations to celebrate certain events, tours and youth camps, religious symposia, religious music concerts, etc.

In 2019, it is estimated that one third of the 1.4 billion international tourist arrivals traveled for religious purposes (approximately 450 million people). The popularity of faith-based tourism cannot be underestimated, as even 25% of travelers are interested in this type of tourism. Estimates for Romania for the year 2019 show that approximately 1,000,000 were religiously motivated tourists.

For the development of religious tourism, its potential should be intertwined with activities that promote religious tourism and its organization.

Romania has a rich potential for religious tourism famous especially domestically and internationally recognized by combining with cultural tourism. Religious tourism infrastructure is growing, both quantitatively and qualitatively. Every year, Romania is visited by many tourists in the main geographical regions: Bucovina, Moldova, Transylvania, Oltenia, Muntenia, Dobrogea, Banat, Crișana. Each of these regions is individualized by something special, from history, to architectural style, painting, traditions or customs.

The 2017 UNWTO Religious Tourism Conference in Fatima provided an invigorating perspective on the growing recognition of this sector by national and international agencies. It has been highlighted that religious / spiritual tourism can even promote both personal and societal transformation, mainly by focusing on spirituality or by offering experiences that make tourists reflect on their life and worldviews.

The COVID-19 pandemic has affected every tourist segment. All forms of tourism have experienced significant declines, given that almost all attractions and accommodation have had to be closed, at least temporarily.

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